

Microplastic Analysis in FTIR Images with *Purency Microplastics Finder* R2021a

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Figure 1. Visualization of the ground truth (left) and the particles detected by *Purency Microplastics Finder* (right)

Abbreviations

EVAc, Ethylene-vinyl acetate; FP, false positive; FN, false negative; IR, infrared; MP, microplastic; PA, polyamide; PBT, polybutylene terephthalate; PC, polycarbonate; PE, polyethylene; PET, polyethylene terephthalate; PLA, polylactic acid; PMMA, polymethyl methacrylate; PP, polypropylene; PS, polystyrene; PU, polyurethane; PVC, polyvinyl chloride; TP, true positive; TN, true negative

Introduction

Hyperspectral imaging has revolutionized microplastics (MP) analysis with its speed and exactness. Today, Fourier-Transform Infrared (FTIR) imaging is one of the most frequently used techniques to detect MP in various samples, ranging from drinking water to environmental samples like sediments or biota. However, the analysis of IR spectra requires accurate, fast, and automated analysis. To solve this task, Purency offers a machine-learning based solution called *Microplastics Finder*. To test its performance, the *Microplastics Finder*, release R2021a, was utilized to detect MP particles in an FTIR image of MP reference particles.

Test principle

The reference FTIR image RefIMP contains 938 MP particles* of the most common plastic types, sized 11 to 666 μm. It was recorded using an Agilent Cary 620/670 FTIR imaging system in transmission mode. Using the script MPVal (Weisser, Pohl *et al.* 2022), the particles detected by *Purency Microplastics Finder* were compared to RefIMP: each detected particle was assigned to a ground truth particle based on their coordinates. Then, their classes (plastic types) were compared. Depending on the result, the detected particle was counted as true/false positive/negative (TP/FP/TN/FN), see Figure 2. Based on this evaluation, typical error types were described and performance metrics calculated.

*938 MP particles belonging to classes that are included in Purency Microplastics Finder

Figure 2. Illustration of the assignment of predicted particles to the ground truth and their assignments as TP, FP, or FN of the corresponding classes. Not shown: complementary TN results. Adapted from (Weisser, Pohl *et al.* 2022)

Performance Overview

The particles contained in RefIMP are shown on the left side of Figure 1; the right side shows the particles detected by *Purency Microplastics Finder*. Clearly, both images are congruent to some extent, but there are also some differences. Figure 4 gives a more detailed insight: *Purency Microplastics Finder* predicted almost twice as many particles as are actually contained in RefIMP. It correctly identified (TP) 458 out of 938 particles without over-segmenting them. When including over-segmented particles with fragments assigned to the true particle class, a total of 680 particles (72.5%) were identified correctly.

The greatest source of error were overlooked particles (FN, 211 cases). In turn, *Purency Microplastics Finder* performed very well in avoiding FP results (ghost particles and false type predictions).

Wrong class predictions and over-segmentation

Purency Microplastics Finder predicted the wrong class in only 20 cases. The heatmap in Figure 5 shows more details. It is structured similarly to a classical confusion matrix, however, it additionally shows overlooked, over-segmented, and ghost particles.

Accordingly, PP was confused for PE in almost every second case. However, importantly, also 37% of PP particles were over-segmented. Taken together, this indicates that PP particles were over-segmented and some segments were wrongly classified as PE, as can be seen in Figure 3. Regardless of the identification method used, misclassification is a very common problem at particle edges, where spectra are often noisy and distorted (Renner, Schmidt *et al.* 2017).

Another class highly prone to over-segmentation and wrong class prediction is PLA, which in many cases was segmented into fragments assigned to PLA, PMMA, and EVAc. Due to their structural similarities, the IR

spectra of these three plastics are difficult to distinguish, even for human experts.

Overlooked particles

The main source of error were overlooked particles: 211 particles (22.5%) were not found, belonging to the classes PU (94 particles), PLA (35 particles), PE (29 particles), and PS (28 particles).

A possible explanation for overlooking PU and PLA is the inhomogeneity of these two plastics: PU can be produced from a broad variety of monomers (Chattopadhyay and Raju 2007). Consequently, PU materials exhibit varying mechanical properties and IR spectra. Therefore, a model trained to detect one type of PU struggles in detecting other PU types. This is likely the case here. The same is assumed for PLA, which contains up to 30% plasticizers (Farah, Anderson *et al.* 2016), potentially influencing the IR spectrum.

The reason for overlooking ~25% of both PE and PS particles seems to lay in the poor quality of their spectra in RefIMP. They are very noisy, thus substantially impeding the classification.

Ghost particles

Purency Microplastics Finder detected only 85 ghost particles. The classes affected were PBT, PMMA, and PA. The latter were caused by misinterpretation of protein particles. The *Microplastics Finder* has not been trained for classifying protein spectra, which can explain the misinterpretation.

However, due to their structure, PA and protein spectra are very similar and hard to distinguish even for human experts. Apart from PBT, the classes not present in RefIMP did not lead to FP results, underlining the high specificity of the model for these classes.

Figure 4. Overall performance of *Purency Microplastics Finder* and most common error types

Figure 3. Example of an over-segmented PP particle (orange) with FP PE fragments (pink).

Figure 5. Heatmap summarizing the performance of *Purency Microplastics Finder* on RefIMP

Summary

Purency Microplastics Finder classified MP particles in RefIMP at an overall accuracy of 0.768. The greatest sources of error were over-segmentation of PP and PLA particles and overlooking of PU, PS, and PE particles. In practice, the over-segmented particles will require manual correction at a manageable extent. Same holds true for ‘ghost particles’, which need to be deleted from the results manually.

According to this test, application of the *Microplastics Finder* can be expected to lead to false class predictions close to zero, showing the high reliability of the algorithm.

Class	Quantity in RefIMP	<i>Purency Microplastics Finder</i>
PE	97	68
PP	71	67
PVC	92	85
PA	94	76
PS	98	70
PLA	83	48
PMMA	124	102
PU	103	9
PC	89	77
PET	87	78
Total MP	948	606

References

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